

Leucocarbo melanogensis
Crozet shag

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© A. Makhado

Group: Bird

Size: 70 cm (height) 125 cm (wingspan)

Distribution:

Prince Edward and Crozet Islands

Importance:

This species is critically endangered due to reduced breeding success and inhabits a relatively small geographic area. This genome will be used as a reference genome for future conservation genetics work.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 65.49 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.48 thousand bases (kilobases)

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 1.22 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness: 98.8% [Single: 98.0%, Duplicated: 0.8%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 2 723.9 kilobases

Contig number: 3 739

Sample Contributor contact details:

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